

D4.3: ATLAS ON CLIMATE RISK

ANALYSIS OF CLIMATE HAZARDS AS RISK FACTORS TO LAND-BASED MITIGATION TECHNOLOGIES
IN MULTI-MODEL CLIMATE SIMULATIONS AND MULTIPLE FUTURE CLIMATE SCENARIOS

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LANDMARC

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Short Summary of results	
<p>Land-based mitigation techniques (LMTs) are crucial to limit future climate change, and at the same time these LMTs are exposed to the changing climate conditions which can pose risks to the LMTs as such and their efficacy. This report analyses a range of climate-related risk factors that have been previously identified, in particular hot, dry and compound hot and dry climate extremes, as well as extreme wind speeds in relation to winter storms. We present a comprehensive analysis of how these different climate hazards are changing in a range of future climate scenarios simulated by the state-of-the-art climate models provided as part of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6).</p> <p>The results indicate that the intensity, frequency and duration of heat extremes are expected to increase in all land regions globally during the 21st century. The magnitude of these increases is proportional to the future greenhouse gas emissions, i.e. strong mitigation efforts promise to efficiently limit the increases in these climate hazards. The changes in dry extremes depend on the specific measures used to quantify drought. Drought indices based on precipitation alone indicate increasing drought occurrence in the Mediterranean region, northern South America, southern Africa and large part of Australia, while drought occurrence decreases in particular in high northern latitudes, consistent with the increase in rainfall in these regions. Drought indices based on precipitation and evapotranspiration (i.e. also taking the atmospheric water demand into account) show a more widespread increase in drought occurrence in the future climate projections, in particular in large areas of North and South America, central and southern Europe, northern and southern Africa, southern and central Asia and Australia. Changes in the compound hot and dry extremes are also sensitive to how exactly drought is measured, but show overall a widespread increase in the frequency of such compound extremes in large parts of the globe (the only regions where these compound extremes do not consistently increase are those where the drought occurrence decreases in the climate projections). Finally, analysing changes in extreme wind speeds and related loss potentials, we find these to decrease in northern</p>	

and southern Europe, but to increase along a belt around the southern North Sea, including southern UK, northern France, BeNeLux, Denmark and parts of Germany.

Showing the results of regional projections (targeted at 44 IPCC reference regions) for the range of hot and dry extremes results in a large number of figures that form part of the climate risk atlas. Therefore, to facilitate the exploration of regional changes in climate extremes in the different IPCC reference regions, we provide a Web-App where users can select to see the results for their specific region of interest and the most relevant climate extremes.

Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world’s climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors,
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions,
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs,

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia, and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g., climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Purpose of this document

This document reports on the analysis of climate hazards, being a key contributor to climate-related risks, in the climate projections from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6). These CMIP6 climate projections represent the latest and most comprehensive database of coordinated climate change projections following different scenarios.

The report summarises different studies that analyse a selection of different climate extremes, which were identified as important risk factors to the Land-based Mitigation Techniques (LMTs), in particular hot and dry extremes, compound hot and dry extremes, and extreme wind speeds in relation to wind storms.

This report further documents a Web-App that facilitates the display and exploration of regional changes in these climate extremes.

1. Introduction

Limiting future climate change to global warming levels consistent with the goals of the Paris Agreement will heavily rely on techniques that remove carbon from the atmosphere and store it in e.g. the land surface or ocean. Land-based Mitigation Techniques (LMTs) are a key component of such carbon removal and storage approaches, and often involve vegetation. These LMTs, however, are also exposed to the climate, including climate extremes, which can put at risk their carbon storage efficacy. This Deliverable report therefore explores a range of future climate hazards that can pose risk to LMT implementations under different future emission scenarios.

The LANDMARC Deliverables D4.1 and D4.2 have surveyed and analysed the climate conditions that pose most risk to the LMT implementations at different scales. Based on both stakeholder interviews (D4.1) and analysis of remote sensing data (D4.2), hot and dry conditions have been identified as posing a particularly strong risk to a variety of LMTs, in particular to those LMTs involving vegetation. Hot and dry conditions are also often associated with increased risk of fires. In addition, the stakeholder surveys also identified storms and the associated strong winds as relevant risk factor for some LMTs, such as forest. These findings are also consistent with information gathered in other databases containing information on LMT risks, outside of the LANDMARC project, such as the World Overview of Conservation Approaches and Technologies (WOCAT) Global Database on Sustainable Land Management¹.

While the identification of specific quantitative thresholds (e.g. high temperature values) above which the risk or damage occurs has proven difficult due to strong dependence on specific location and species used for LMTs (see LANDMARC Deliverable D4.2), the different lines of information point to qualitatively similar types of events posing risk. In this report (and the associated studies) we therefore make use of some widely established indices for hot and dry extremes. These include indices with variations in their exact definition, which has been a deliberate choice for this work. To account for the difficulty (or in fact no reasonable definition) to provide clear quantitative risk thresholds (based on the surveys and analysis in D4.1 and D4.2), we chose to assess the robustness of changes for a variety of different extremes indices.

This report corresponds largely to the published peer-reviewed journal publication by De Luca and Donat (2023), for the study of hot and dry extremes. And for the analysis of wind storm loss potential, the report contains material that was produced in the context of the Master thesis by Iñaki Otero Antero (Otero Antero, 2023).

Socio-economic and environmental impacts of hot, dry, and compound hot-dry meteorological extremes can pose a significant distress to natural and socio-economic systems worldwide

¹ <https://www.wocat.net/en/global-slm-database/>

(Barriopedro et al., 2011; Zscheischler & Fischer, 2020; Zscheischler et al., 2018). It is therefore of paramount importance to provide information on how these meteorological hazards may change in the future under anthropogenic climate change.

There is now a general consensus about a global increase in hot extremes under anthropogenic climate change (e.g., Christidis et al., 2015; Fischer & Schär, 2010; Perkins-Kirkpatrick & Lewis, 2020), with such trend mainly attributed to thermodynamic changes, or to an increase in global mean temperature (Rastogi et al., 2020; Vogel, Zscheischler, et al., 2020) and local land-atmosphere feedbacks (Donat et al., 2017; Seneviratne et al., 2006), with also changes in the atmospheric circulation playing a role for example, in Eurasia and North America (Horton et al., 2015; Rousi et al., 2022; Schielicke & Pfahl, 2022; Suarez-Gutierrez et al., 2020). Future projected changes in drought are sensitive to the index used (Cook et al., 2018; Dai, 2011, 2013). This is because drought can be computed from precipitation alone (McKee et al., 1993) and also from the combination of precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (PET) (Palmer, 1965; Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010), with the latter case taking into account the effect of increasing temperatures. Future changes in drought based on precipitation deficit point toward an increase in dryness over northern South America, the Mediterranean, southern Africa and South Australia (Ukkola et al., 2020). On the other hand, projections of drought computed from precipitation and PET show increased dryness over the same regions as Ukkola et al. (2020) and also in Central and central-north America, most of the African continent, central Europe, the Middle East, southeast Asia and Australia (Dai, 2011, 2013). Lastly, changes in drought can be also sensitive to the equation used to approximate PET, as shown in Begueria et al. (2014). Other factors playing a role in shaping drought events in the short-term over some of these regions are sea-surface temperatures anomalies, weakened summer Asian monsoons and likely changes in atmospheric circulation patterns (Dai, 2011, 2013; Schubert et al., 2016; Teuling et al., 2013; Trenberth et al., 2014).

Hot and dry extremes can also concur concurrently (or within a time-frame of a few weeks) at a location (Bevacqua et al., 2022; Hao et al., 2018; Manning et al., 2019; Mukherjee et al., 2022, 2023; Zscheischler et al., 2018, 2020) – often called a compound hot and dry event. Such compound events are of particular interest because these can lead to larger impacts, e.g. on natural systems, compared to the univariate hot or dry extremes. Reflecting the changes in (uni-variate) hot and dry extremes, also compound hot-dry extremes are set to increase under anthropogenic climate change (Bevacqua et al., 2022; Ridder et al., 2022; Vogel et al., 2020) and they appear to be modulated by mean precipitation trends (Bevacqua et al., 2022). Most of these studies consider hot, dry and hot-dry compound extremes separately, hindering a robust understanding of how these types of extremes relate to each other. Moreover, they do not use different metrics for the computation of dry extremes, also on several accumulation periods, such as indices that consider precipitation and precipitation along with evaporative water demand, that can in turn affect dry and compound hot-dry extreme changes.

Here we build on these works and provide a comprehensive analysis of projected changes in hot, dry and compound hot-dry extremes over global land regions. We use a multi-model ensemble (MME) of

25 Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) models (Eyring et al., 2016), four emission scenarios, and a suite of different univariate and compound extreme indices. Such indices consider different aspects of drought, such as precipitation and evaporative water demand over multiple accumulation periods, also in compound extremes, which in combination allows us to discuss how the changes in compound extremes relate to their univariate hot and dry contributions.

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Data

We use CMIP6 data (Eyring et al., 2016), namely historical and future Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP) (O'Neill et al., 2016) simulations. From the ScenarioMIP we use four Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs): SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5 – which correspond to four different future scenarios of political and socioeconomic developments, resulting in different trajectories of future greenhouse gas emissions, and accordingly different levels of global warming. From these simulations we extract daily maximum near-surface temperature (t_{max} , K), daily minimum near-surface temperature (t_{min} , K) and daily precipitation (pr , $kg \cdot m^{-2} \cdot s^{-1}$), respectively for the periods 1950–2014 and 2015–2100, for a MME of 25 models (Supplementary Table S1 in Appendix I). These daily climate model outputs are then used to calculate the climate extremes indices (see Sections 2.2 and 2.3). From each model we only considered the first ensemble member available (in most cases $r1i1p1f1$) so that models' structural uncertainty is taken into account (Deser, 2020).

2.2 Hot and Dry Extremes Indices

We compute a selection of extreme indices to quantify global hot and dry extremes from 1950 to 2100, using 1981–2010 as a baseline period for the calculation of percentile thresholds. The indices are computed starting in 1949 to avoid obtaining incomplete index calculations in 1950 for indices that accumulate across calendar years, namely the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI, McKee et al., 1993) and Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI, Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). For hot extremes we calculate the percentage of days when daily maximum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile ($tx90p$) and the annual maximum of daily maximum temperatures (txx) (Zhang et al., 2011). We also calculate three indices measuring heatwave characteristics, where heatwaves are considered as periods of at least three consecutive days when daily maximum temperatures exceed the 90th percentile (Perkins & Alexander, 2013). The heatwave amplitude (hwa_{tx90}) represents the annual peak daily value ($^{\circ}C$) in the hottest heatwave, the heatwave duration (hwd_{tx90}) refers to the length (days) of the longest heatwave within a year and heatwave frequency (hwf_{tx90}) measures the number of days within a year that contribute to heatwaves (<https://climimpact-sci.org/>).

To quantify the occurrence of dry extremes we use the SPI and SPEI with 3-, 6-, and 12-month accumulation periods. The SPI provides information about meteorological drought in terms of lack of precipitation, whereas the SPEI in terms of lack of water availability by considering also the atmospheric water demand. SPI and SPEI include the entire precipitation, or precipitation minus PET, distributions, and do not directly indicate drought occurrences. A caveat is that PET may overestimate drought in very dry regions, where actual evapotranspiration may be lower than PET due to lack of water. We define drought when these monthly index values are below or equal -1 , which represents moderate drought conditions. We use -1 as threshold to ensure a sufficient number of monthly values for statistical analyses within the SPI and SPEI drought data sets, but lower values could be used as criterion for more severe drought. As a baseline for the estimation of the distribution parameters we use the entire investigation period (151 years, 1950–2100) (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2020), to avoid potential biases outside relatively short reference periods as reported for example, by Sippel et al. (2015). To allow comparison across SSPs, we use the SPI and SPEI distribution parameters derived for the Historical and one SSP scenario (i.e., SSP1-2.6) to compute SPI and SPEI in the other scenarios. We use SSP1-2.6 because this is the scenario with smallest forcing changes. For the SPEI we compute PET following Hargreaves (1994), which is based on maximum and minimum temperatures (K), and latitude to estimate extraterrestrial radiation. SPEI results can be sensitive to how PET is calculated (e.g., Beguería et al., 2014). Therefore, we also assessed the sensitivity of SPEI to different PET approximations, that is, following Thornthwaite (1948), and the more complex Penman method (Allen et al., 1994). We performed this comparison for two CMIP6 models, under SSP5-8.5 and SSP2-4.5, for *spei3*, *spei6* and *spei12*. We found that annual global mean time-series are in agreement between the Hargreaves and Penman methods, but using the Thornthwaite method results in much stronger drying. Similarly, for the drought occurrence measured as *spei3_dry*, *spei6_dry*, and *spei12_dry* there is good agreement between calculations using the Hargreaves and Penman methods, but a stronger and more wide-spread increase in drought occurrence is found with the Thornthwaite method. For the comprehensive analysis of the full MME we therefore calculate PET using the Hargreaves method which gives relatively similar results to the more complex Penman approximation but requires less data. We use the index names *spiN_dry* and *speiN_dry* to refer to the count of dry months, where N stands for the accumulation period of the index (i.e., 3, 6, and 12 months).

2.3 Compound Extremes

We also compute indices that measure the occurrence of (same-day) compound hot-dry extremes. We define this index as *cex_d*, which stands for “compound extreme days.” Here we use *tasmax* extremes exceeding the 90th percentile (similar to *tx90p*, as indicator for hot extremes), SPI and SPEI (3, 6, and 12-month) monthly values ≤ -1 (as indicator for dry extremes). The *tasmax* percentiles are computed from SSP1-2.6 during the entire 1950–2100 period, to make it consistent with the SPI and SPEI baselines, and serve as threshold for extreme temperatures in all SSP scenarios. In order to

homogenize the temporal frequencies of the datasets, the SPI and SPEI original monthly time-series are converted into daily time-series by setting each daily value to the SPI and SPEI monthly value in which the day occurs.

The *cex_d* index assesses the occurrence of same-day compound hot-dry extremes and is computed as follows: (a) identify daily hot extremes (tasmax >90th percentile) and daily dry extremes (SPI and SPEI ≤ -1); (b) count the number of days with compound (same-day) hot-dry extremes or when the hot days coincide with the occurrence of dry days. We name compound extremes calculated with SPI ≤ -1 as *cex_d (spiN)* and compound extremes computed with SPEI ≤ -1 as *cex_d (speiN)*, where *N* stands for the number of accumulated months (i.e., 3, 6, or 12).

Table 1: List and definition of extreme hot and dry climate indices analysed in this report. (*) heatwaves are defined when the maximum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile on 3 consecutive days.

Index	Index name	Description
tx90p	Warm day frequency	percentage of days when daily maximum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile
txx	Hottest day of the year	annual maximum of daily maximum temperatures
hwa_tx90	heatwave amplitude	annual peak daily value (°C) in the hottest heatwave*
hwd_tx90	Heatwave duration	length (days) of the longest heatwave* within a year
Hwf_Tx90	Heatwave frequency	number of days within a year that contribute to heatwaves*
spiN_dry	Meteorological Drought months	Number of months per year when the Standardised Precipitation Index accumulated over N months is ≤ -1
speiN_dry	Hydrological Drought months	Number of months per year when the Standardised Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index accumulated over N months is ≤ -1
<i>cex_d (spiN)</i>	Annual number of compound hot and dry days (based on SPI)	Annual count of days for which the daily maximum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile and the SPI (accumulated over N months) is ≤ -1
<i>cex_d (speiN)</i>	Annual number of compound hot and dry days (based on SPEI)	Annual count of days for which the daily maximum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile and the SPEI (accumulated over N months) is ≤ -1

2.4 Extreme wind speeds and loss potentials

For the analysis of extreme wind speeds and related loss potentials in relation to winter storms in Europe, we use daily maximum wind speeds from the CMIP6 simulations. The analysis of the changes in winter storminess focuses on the SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios, considering the winter half year October to March.

Storm-related damages and losses often occur for wind speeds exceeding the 98th percentile, i.e. roughly on the 2% windiest days (Klawa and Ulbrich, 2003). When analysing changes in extreme wind speeds, we therefore present changes for the 98th percentile. Furthermore, we use this 98th percentile

as threshold for potential damages or losses in the storm loss model. Following previous research (e.g. Klawns and Ulbrich, 2003; Donat et al., 2011), we calculate a loss index that estimates the loss potentials as a cubic function of wind speeds exceeding the loss threshold:

$$\text{loss potential} = \left(\frac{v_{98}}{v_{\max}} - 1 \right) \quad \text{for } v_{\max} > v_{98},$$

$$\text{loss potential} = 0 \quad \text{for } v_{\max} \leq v_{98}$$

Where v_{\max} is the maximum wind speed registered on a given day, and v_{98} the 98th percentile of daily maximum wind speeds during the reference period.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

We calculate all the indices on the native CMIP6 model grids and then re-grid them to a common latitude-longitude grid of $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ so that MME medians and percentiles can be computed across all models. We then remove the ocean grid-points with a land-sea mask in order to retain only land values and exclude Antarctica. Then, for each index we compute the MME median along with the MME interquartile range (25th and 75th percentiles), the latter used as a measure of inter-model uncertainty.

To discuss the projected changes in extremes, we present annual global average time-series (weighted by gridpoint area) and maps of end-of-century changes relative to recent climate conditions. Regional average time series for 44 land-based IPCC reference regions (Iturbide et al., 2020) are shown in the Appendix II and a web-based app to interactively explore the large amount of regional figures (this web app is described in Section 5). In the (global and regional) time series we assess the MME medians using the modified Mann-Kendall test that takes into account autocorrelation (Hamed & Ramachandra Rao, 1998) and also compute the Sen's slopes of the time-series (Sen, 1968). From the modified Mann-Kendall test we extract the p -values of the MME median trends. We calculate the global maps of changes by taking the difference of MME medians (computed from single-model 20-year averages) between two periods, namely the four future projected SSPs during 2081–2100 and the historical simulations during 1981–2000. We assess the statistical significance of the resulting end-of-century changes, for each grid-point, with a two-tailed Wilcoxon rank-sum test (Mann & Whitney, 1947) that assesses if the median values are significantly different and does not assume data normally distributed. Then, we further correct the p -values obtained with a Bonferroni correction (Bonferroni, 1936; Sedgwick, 2014) that takes into account Type I errors (or false positives) in relation to multiple testing.

As a further assessment to indicate the robustness of the simulated changes across models, we also apply a sign-test, which tests for each gridpoint if at least 80% ($n = 20$) of models have a difference value of the same sign (positive or negative).

3. Simulated Changes in Extremes

3.1 Hot Extremes

The maps of changes in the SSP5-8.5 scenario show widespread significant increases in the different hot extremes indices, consistent with an overall warming climate (Figures 1a, 1c, 1e, 1g, and 1i). The *tx90p* index shows pronounced increase in the frequency of hot extremes over northern South America, western, central and eastern Africa, the Arabian peninsula, the Tibetan plateau and Indonesia (Figure 1a), whereas *txx* shows largest increases in the intensity of hot extremes over central South America, central north America and Europe (Figure 1c). The *hwa_tx90* shows global relatively homogeneous patterns of increased heatwave amplitude, however with largest increases over central north America, parts of Brazil and Europe (Figure 1e). The *hwd_tx90* index points toward substantial increase in the duration of heatwaves over northern Africa and the Arabian peninsula (Figure 1g), whereas the *hwf_tx90* index shows overall large increases in heatwave frequency, especially over northern and central parts of South America, northern Africa, the Arabian peninsula and Indonesia (Figure 1i). Similar spatial patterns of projected changes by the end of the 21st century, although less pronounced in terms of statistical significance and magnitude, are obtained for the other SSP scenarios (Figure S1–S5 in Supporting Information Appendix I). The smaller increases in the lower-forcing scenarios (i.e., SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP3-7.0) point to the benefits of implementing strong and effective mitigation measures (O’Neill et al., 2016). Looking at the global average time-series, the MME of historical climate simulations shows relatively slow increase during the late 20th and early 21st centuries, as compared to the future high-forcing SSP scenarios. The historical simulations also show substantial reductions for the duration of 1–2 years in particular in the global average intensity of heat extremes (e.g., *txx* and *hwa_tx90*) in response to, for example, the Pinatubo volcanic eruption in 1991 (Figures 1b, 1d, 1f, and 1j). In the future projections, all indices point toward increases in hot extremes, with SSP5-8.5 being the scenario with most pronounced increases, SSP1-2.6 being the one with more moderate changes, and SSP2-4.5 with SSP3-7.0 lying between the two (Figures 1b, 1d, 1f, 1h, and 1j, $p < 0.01$)—indicating proportionality between the magnitude of change and the strength of the forcing (Seneviratne et al., 2016). Regional average time series for the different IPCC reference regions are shown in the Appendix II and in the Shiny App described in Section 5.

Figure 1: Multi-model ensemble (MME) difference maps and global land average time-series of hot extremes. Maps show MME median changes between the SSP8-8.5 2081–2100 and historical 1981–2000 time slices, and time-series show MME medians (colored lines) and interquartile ranges (gray shading) for the historical and Shared Socioeconomic Pathway scenarios. (a–b) *tx90p*; (c–d) *txx*; (e–f) *hwa_tx90p*; (g–h) *hwd_tx90p*; and (i–j) *hwf_tx90p*. In (a, c, e, g, and i) stippling indicates gridpoints where the difference is not statistically significant ($p \geq 0.05$) or that did not pass the sign-test ($\leq 80\%$).

3.2 Dry Extremes

Results for global dry extremes (Figure 2) differ depending on index, and therefore atmospheric variables taken into consideration, as also shown by Cook et al. (2018). The end-of-century changes for *spi3_dry* under the SSP5-8.5scenario point toward both drying and wetting in different regions

across the globe, reflecting for example, annual mean precipitation changes reported by the IPCC AR6 (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2021; Figure SPM.5c). Hence, we find a significant ($p < 0.05$ and sign-test $>80\%$) projected increase in drought occurrence (based on SPI) in central and South America, the Mediterranean basin and southern Africa. Whereas drought occurrence is projected to decrease over central Africa, India, China and in high northern latitudes (e.g., Alaska, Canada, Scandinavia, and Russia; Figure 2a). Such heterogeneity in the difference maps is reflected in the global average time-series, which show a non-linear trend that cannot be assessed with a Slope value (Figure 2b). Specifically, the *spi3_dry* values of the historical period increase from 1950 to about the 1970s and then decrease until the end of the historical forcing runs in 2014. Following the historical period the global average *spi3_dry* values for SSP5-8.5 and SSP3-7.0 increase until the end of the 21st century, with the former showing the strongest upward trend, while the SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6 global average time series remain relatively stationary (Figure 2b). However, although some global average time-series are showing little changes, the regional patterns of drying and wetting still remain in place (Figures S6 and S7 in Supporting Information Appendix I), but compensate each other in the global average. The results suggest that at stronger forcing levels (SSP5-8.5 and SSP3-7.0) the drought increases found in some tropical and subtropical regions overcompensate the drought decreases in the high northern latitudes.

Figure 2: Multi-model ensemble difference maps and global land average time-series of dry extremes. (a–b) Annual count of dry months computed with Standardized Precipitation Index 3-month index (*spi3_dry*); (c–d) annual count of dry months computed with Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index 3-month index (*spei3_dry*). Time-periods, stippling, and time-series colors are as in Figure 1.

The picture is different when considering the count of dry months computed from SPEI and therefore by taking into account PET along with precipitation (*spei3_dry*; Figures 2c and 2d). Here, the end-of-century changes for SSP5-8.5 project a drying over much larger areas compared to SPI-based drought,

with regions such as northern Africa, the Mediterranean, the Middle East and central China being the most affected, while only very small regions in high northern latitudes show decreases in drought occurrence based on this measure (Figure 2c). This much wider spread of drought increases is also reflected in the global average time series, which show upward trends from about 2015 to 2100 under all scenarios, with SSP5-8.5 being the one with the largest increases and SSP1-2.6 becoming stationary from about the 2050s. The other two scenarios, SSP3-7.0 and SSP2-4.5, lie between the two, again indicating a proportionality of the global drought response to the strength of forcing. Such a larger increase in dryness from *spei3_dry* compared to *spi3_dry* is expected as with warming temperatures also the atmospheric water demand increases (e.g., Pall et al., 2007).

The difference maps for the other *spi3_dry* and *spei3_dry* SSP scenarios have similar spatial patterns as shown in Figures 2a and 2c. However, from SSP3-7.0 to SSP1-2.6, we note that for *spi3_dry* the areas with decreasing drought occurrences increase (Figure S6), whereas for *spei3_dry* the areas with increasing drought counts decrease in scenarios with weaker forcing (Figure S7).

The difference maps for *spi6_dry*, *spei6_dry*, *spi12_dry* and *spei12_dry* show very similar patterns as found in Figures 2a and 2c, however the statistical significance is sometimes lower, especially for the *spi12_dry* and *spei12_dry*. Also for these drought indices, the regional average time series for the IPCC reference regions are available in the Appendix II and the Shiny App described in Section 5.

3.3 Compound Hot-Dry Extremes

The end-of-century changes for compound hot-dry extremes, under the SSP5-8.5 scenario show a widespread increase in the occurrence of such events (Figures 3a and 3c). For *cex_d (spi3)* the regions showing stronger increase in compound hot-dry extremes are central and northern South America, central Europe, the Mediterranean, western and southern Africa and Indonesia (Figure 3a). Compound hot-dry extremes computed with *cex_d (spei3)* show large increases over the same areas mentioned above but also in northern Africa, the Middle East, and Australia (Figure 3c). For *cex_d (spi3)* there are areas in high northern latitudes with no increase in compound extremes and this is related to the decreased drought frequency in these regions (Figures 3a and 2a). On the other hand, *cex_d (spei3)* shows significant increases globally (Figure 3b).

Figure 3: Multi-model ensemble difference maps and global land average time-series of compound hot-dry extremes. (a–b) Annual number of compound hot-dry extremes computed with daily maximum near-surface temperature and SPI3. (c–d) same as (a–b) but with SPEI3. Time-periods, stippling and time-series colors are as in Figure 1.

In accordance with the difference maps of both *cex_d (spi3)* and *cex_d (spei3)*, also the median of annual and global average time-series show strong monotonic and positive trends for all the SSP scenarios from about 2015 to 2100, except for the SSP1-2.6 in which the compound extreme occurrences stabilize around the 2050s ($p < 0.01$). As for the univariate extremes presented in the previous sections, the SSP5-8.5 is the scenario with the strongest increases, followed by SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6 (Figures 3b and 3d) and changes in compound extremes computed with SPEI to detect drought are much stronger than compound extremes computed with SPI.

The *cex_d (spi3)* and *cex_d (spei3)* difference maps computed for the other SSP scenarios show similar changes as for SSP5-8.5, although the magnitudes and statistical significance are reduced from SSP3-7.0 to SSP1-2.6 (Figures S8 and S9 in Supporting Information Appendix I). Also the difference maps of *cex_d (spi6) (spei6) (spi12)* and *(spei12)* reflect the changes similar to *cex_d (spi3)* and *(spei3)*, with both magnitude and statistical significance reduced from SSP5-8.5 to SSP1-2.6 and from *cex_d (spi12, spei12)* to *cex_d (spi3, spei3)* (Figures S10–S13 in Supporting Information Appendix I).

3.4 Extreme wind speeds and storm loss potentials

The projections of future changes in extreme winds, are relatively similar between the two future scenarios analysed. In both scenarios (see Figure 4), the general trend over most of Europe is a decrease in the 98th percentile of daily maximum wind speeds, which translates into a reduction of

wind speeds capable of causing storm damage. The strongest decreases in extreme wind speeds are observed over Iceland, northern Scandinavia, the Mediterranean region and Poland. Generally, the more aggressive the scenario, the more significant the changes, except for the case of Poland. Changes observed in these areas vary between -0.3 and -0.7 m/s in the SSP2-4.5 scenario (see Figure 4a) and between -0.5 and -1.0 m/s in the SSP5-8.5 scenario (see Figure 4b). However, there are some regions where an increase in extreme wind speeds can be observed. These regions differ a bit between the future scenarios, but the areas with most noticeable increases in both scenarios are the regions surrounding the south of the North Sea (England, northern France, BeNeLux, Germany) and the regions around the Baltic Sea (southern Scandinavia, Estonia and Latvia), with increases varying between 0-0.2 m/s in the SSP2-4.5 scenario and between 0.1-0.4 m/s in the SSP5-8.5 scenario. Other areas where increases are observed in only one of the two future scenarios include the regions surrounding the Black Sea (Ukraine, Turkey, Caucasus), with increases only in the SSP2-4.5 scenario, and central-west Russia, with increases only for SSP5-8.5.

Figure 4: Projected changes for the end of the 21st century (2081-2100 minus 1981-2000) of the 98th percentile of daily maximum wind speeds for SSP2-4.5 scenario (a) and SSP5-8.5 scenario (b). All units are m/s.

Future variations in extreme wind speeds would be expected to cause similar variations in the economic or natural losses caused by winter storms. An increase in extreme wind speeds will probably cause an increase in winter storm losses, while a decrease in extreme wind speeds is expected to cause a decrease in winter storm losses. This becomes quite clear in Figure 5. The changes of the accumulated loss index for the future scenarios display a strong spatial correlation with the changes of the 98th percentile of daily maximum wind speeds.

Similarly to the changes in extreme wind speeds, the general trend seen in Figure 5 for the accumulated loss index in Europe is a decrease in the majority of areas. The regions with the strongest decreases in the accumulated loss index are more or less consistent between both future scenarios, including Iceland, northern Scandinavia, western Mediterranean (especially the Iberian Peninsula) and eastern Europe (especially Poland). However, there are also regions where the accumulated loss index increases. Some of these regions, like the territories around the south of the North Sea (England, Germany, BeNeLux, northern France), the coastal Baltic regions (southern Scandinavia, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania), the Russia-Belarus-Ukraine bordering region and the Iraq-Iran bordering region are consistent between both future scenarios. Other regions only show increases in either the SSP2-4.5 scenario, like areas around the Black Sea (Ukraine, Turkey, Caucasus), or the SSP5-8.5 scenario, like Romania and central Russia.

Figure 5: Projected changes for the end of the 21st century (2081-2100 minus 1981-2000) of the accumulated loss index for SSP2-4.5 scenario (a) and SSP5-8.5 scenario (b).

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Our results show significant projected increases in the frequency, intensity and duration of hot extremes in most regions by the end of the 21st century, and these increases are strongest for the SSP5-8.5 scenario and weakest for SSP1-2.6. Such increase in hot extremes reflect the findings of other studies (e.g., Christidis et al., 2015; Fischer & Schär, 2010; Mukherjee et al., 2022; Yin et al., 2022) but can quantitatively differ from other studies using different temperature extreme indices (e.g., Saeed et al., 2021).

Dry extremes, on the other hand, show different regional patterns of change depending on the index used to measure drought (i.e., SPI or SPEI). Such a difference is related to the types of variables included in the indices (e.g., precipitation or precipitation and PET) (Dai, 2011, 2013). While there is sensitivity to the specific measures to detect drought, the results are fairly robust for different drought accumulation periods (i.e., 3, 6, and 12 months). Dry extremes computed with SPI, under the SSP5-8.5

scenario, increase over central and northern South America, the Mediterranean and southern Africa and decrease over central Africa, India, China and in the high northern latitudes. On the other hand, dry extremes computed with SPEI show consistent increase generally all over the globe, but especially in the Mediterranean, northern Africa, the Middle East and central China. Our results reflect the expectation that evaporative demand of the atmosphere increases at higher temperatures, and this is a driver of drought when characterized with SPEI. When assessing the global land average time-series, regional drought increases and decreases computed with SPI partly compensate each other and global average increases in drought only occur in the strongest forcing scenarios. On the other hand, the global land averages affected by drought computed with SPEI increase in all scenarios. The increase in dryness can be primarily driven by the changing patterns of precipitation (when based on SPI) and additionally by the increasing atmospheric water demand as the climate warms (when based on SPEI).

Results for compound hot-dry extremes are consistent with the changes in univariate hot and dry extremes and therefore the difference maps for SSP5-8.5 point toward widespread increases in compound hot-dry extremes for indices computed with both SPI (*cex_d (spi3)*, *cex_d (spi6)* and *cex_d (spi12)*) and SPEI (*cex_d (spei3)*, *cex_d (spei6)* and *cex_d (spei12)*). These widespread increases are therefore also reflected in the global land average time series, indicating significant increases by the end of the 21st century in all four scenarios.

Our findings allow a direct comparison between univariate and compound hot-dry extremes and are in accordance with other studies pointing toward an increase in hot-dry compound extremes under anthropogenic climate change. For instance, Bevacqua et al. (2022) found a projected increase in hot-dry extremes and assessed their uncertainty but only using precipitation as a proxy for dry events. Similarly, Hao et al. (2018) and Ridder et al. (2022) computed dry extremes only from precipitation and the latter study used Excess Heat Factor for assessing heatwaves. Our results show that there is some sensitivity in the projected changes with respect to dry and compound hot-dry extremes, attributed to the way dry extremes are measured.

Our analysis framework provides insights from considering the different univariate and compound indices in combination. In particular, we find that global increases in hot extremes alone are driving the increase in compound extremes in regions where dry extremes, computed with SPI, decrease (e.g., northern Europe and China). On the contrary, compound extremes computed with SPEI (and computed with SPI in regions where drought becomes more frequent) are increasing because of the contributions of increasing both univariate hot and dry extremes. The pattern in compound extremes computed with SPI is also in agreement with Bevacqua et al. (2022), who highlighted the role of regional precipitation in driving future changes in compound hot-dry extremes.

The analysis of extreme wind speeds in the European region, and related storm loss potentials, shows a reduction of this type of climate risk in larger areas of Northern and Southern Europe. We, however, also find a belt around the North Sea region (including southern UK, northern France, the BeNeLux countries, Denmark and parts of Germany) where extreme wind speeds and loss potentials in relation to winter storms are simulated to increase, in particular in the future scenario with strongest

greenhouse gas emissions (SSP5-8.5). While the specific reasons for this regional increase in wind storm risk need to be better understood in future work, this finding is consistent with an eastward extension of the North Atlantic storm track.

In summary, we provide a comprehensive global analysis of compound hot-dry extreme changes in the context of the corresponding univariate hot and dry extremes for 25 CMIP6 models and four SSP scenarios. We specifically show that the entire set of extremes are projected to increase in the future under the highest emission scenario (SSP5-8.5) and that such increase could be partly mitigated under the lowest emission scenario (SSP1-2.6). We conclude that the risk of hot and dry extremes will significantly increase in the next decades in many regions, and encourage particular attention from governments and stakeholders worldwide to implement suitable adaptation measures and put into practice strong mitigation policies to limit the increases of such events.

5. R-Shiny App for interactive visualisation of regional projections of hot and dry extremes

The results shown in the main part of this report focus on a global picture of the projected changes in the hot and dry extremes. While the global change maps provide some information regarding regional differences in the changes, regional users or decision-makers may also appreciate time series showing the temporal evolution of projected changes in the different regions. We therefore provide such regional timeseries representing the area-averaged extreme indices for the 43 IPCC 6th Assessment Report reference regions over land (as defined in Iturbide et al., 2020). These regions are also shown again in Figure 6 below, for easier reference. While these regions are still relatively large compared to the size of a small farm or plantation at a specific location, the size of these regions represents the scale at which the global climate projections can provide meaningful information about climate changes.

1	GIC	Greenland/Iceland	23	SAH	Sahara	43	NAU	N.Australia
2	NWN	N.W.North-America	24	WAF	Western-Africa	44	CAU	C.Australia
3	NEN	N.E.North-America	25	CAF	Central-Africa	45	EAU	E.Australia
4	WNA	W.North-America	26	NEAF	N.Eastern-Africa	46	SAU	S.Australia
5	CNA	C.North-America	27	SEAF	S.Eastern-Africa	47	NZ	New-Zealand
6	ENA	E.North-America	28	WSAF	W.Southern-Africa	48	EAN	E.Antarctica
7	NCA	N.Central-America	29	ESAF	E.Southern-Africa	49	WAN	W.Antarctica
8	SCA	S.Central-America	30	MDG	Madagascar	50	ARO	Arctic-Ocean
9-10	CAR	Caribbean	31	RAR	Russian-Arctic	51	NPO	N.Pacific-Ocean
11	NWS	N.W.South-America	32	WSB	W.Siberia	52	EPO	Equatorial.Pacific-Ocean
12	NSA	N.South-America	33	ESB	E.Siberia	53	SPO	S.Pacific-Ocean
13	NES	N.E.South-America	34	RFE	Russian-Far-East	54	NAO	N.Atlantic-Ocean
14	SAM	South-American-Monsoon	35	WCA	W.C.Asia	55	EAO	Equatorial.Atlantic-Ocean
15	SWS	S.W.South-America	36	ECA	E.C.Asia	56	SAO	S.Atlantic-Ocean
16	SES	S.E.South-America	37	TIB	Tibetan-Plateau	57	ARS	Arabian-Sea
17	SSA	S.South-America	38	EAS	E.Asia	58	BOB	Bay-of-Bengal
18	NEU	N.Europe	39	ARP	Arabian-Peninsula	59	EIO	Equatorial.Indic-Ocean
19	WCE	Western&Central-Europe	40	SAS	S.Asia	60	SIO	S.Indic-Ocean
20	EEU	E.Europe	41-42	SEA	S.E.Asia	61	SOO	Southern-Ocean
21-22	MED	Mediterranean						

Figure 6: Definition of the climate reference regions defined for the IPCC 6th Assessment Report (Figure taken from Iturbide et al. 2020).

Showing these results for 17 different climate extremes indices (including different accumulation periods for the SPI and SPEI) for each of the 43 regions results in a large number of figures (as included in Appendix II), which are not easy to navigate. For this reason we also developed an R-Shiny App, which allows to explore this large set of results for interactively, and specifically for a certain region. This interactive Shiny App is available at URL: <https://earth.bsc.es/shiny/LANDMARC/>

In this App, the users can select their specific region of interest from a drop-down menu in the top-left of the page. After this, the users select the climate extremes indices that are of interest to them from the check-boxes below the drop-down menu, and the relevant figures will be shown in the main panel to the right side of the menu (see e.g. Figure 7). It is possible to select several extremes indices at the same time, and the different figures will then be shown below each other. This will help to compare results across these different measures of hot, dry and compound hot and dry extremes for similarity and differences, to gain a more comprehensive impression of the projected changes in the different regions.

The Shiny web app also contains a tab “Documentation”. This tab contains the basic information about the kind of information that it shows, such as a brief explanation of the different extremes indices and the IPCC reference regions, including a reference to the peer-reviewed scientific open-access publication on which these results are based. This should enable users to understand the information shown in this app, even if they do not have this report at hand.

Figure 7: Screenshot of the R-Shiny App to display the regional results. In this example projections for two different indices (SPEI3_{dry} and TX90p) are shown for the Mediterranean region.

6. References

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7. Appendix I: Supplementary Information

CMIP6 model	CMIP6 ensemble member
ACCESS-CM2	r1i1p1f1
ACCESS-ESM1-5	r1i1p1f1
BCC-CSM2-MR	r1i1p1f1
CMCC-ESM2	r1i1p1f1
CNRM-CM6-1	r1i1p1f2
CNRM-ESM2-1	r1i1p1f2
CanESM5	r1i1p1f1
EC-Earth3-Veg-LR	r1i1p1f1
EC-Earth3-Veg	r1i1p1f1
EC-Earth3	r1i1p1f1
FGOALS-g3	r1i1p1f1
GFDL-ESM4	r1i1p1f1
INM-CM4-8	r1i1p1f1
INM-CM5-0	r1i1p1f1
IPSL-CM6A-LR	r1i1p1f1
KACE-1-0-G	r1i1p1f1
MIROC-ES2L	r1i1p1f2
MIROC6	r1i1p1f1
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	r1i1p1f1
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	r1i1p1f1
MRI-ESM2-0	r1i1p1f1
NorESM2-LM	r1i1p1f1
NorESM2-MM	r1i1p1f1
TaiESM1	r1i1p1f1
UKESM1-0-LL	r1i1p1f2

Table S1. List of CMIP6 models and respective ensemble members of daily maximum near-surface temperature (K), daily minimum near-surface temperature (K) and precipitation ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) used in the analyses for each type of time-period and simulation: Historical, SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5.

(a) tx90p ssp370 – hist

(b) tx90p ssp245 – hist

(c) tx90p ssp126 – hist

Figure S 1: Same as Figure 1a but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

Figure S 2: Same as Figure 1c but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) hwa_tx90 ssp370 – hist

(b) hwa_tx90 ssp245 – hist

(c) hwa_tx90 ssp126 – hist

Figure S 3: Same as Figure 1e but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) hwd_tx90 ssp370 – hist

(b) hwd_tx90 ssp245 – hist

(c) hwd_tx90 ssp126 – hist

Figure S 4: Same as Figure 1g but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) hwf_tx90 ssp370 – hist

(b) hwf_tx90 ssp245 – hist

(c) hwf_tx90 ssp126 – hist

Figure S 5: Same as Figure 1i but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) spi3_dry ssp370 – hist

(b) spi3_dry ssp245 – hist

(c) spi3_dry ssp126 – hist

Figure S 6: Same as Figure 2a but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) spei3_dry ssp370 – hist

(b) spei3_dry ssp245 – hist

(c) spei3_dry ssp126 – hist

Figure S 7: Same as Figure 2c but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) cex_d (spi3) ssp370 – hist

(b) cex_d (spi3) ssp245 – hist

(c) cex_d (spi3) ssp126 – hist

Figure S 8: Same as Figure 3a but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) cex_d (spei3) ssp370 – hist

(b) cex_d (spei3) ssp245 – hist

(c) cex_d (spei3) ssp126 – hist

Figure S 9: Same as Figure 3c but for SSP3-7.0, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6.

(a) cex_d (spi6) ssp585 – hist

(b) cex_d (spi6) ssp370 – hist

(c) cex_d (spi6) ssp245 – hist

(d) cex_d (spi6) ssp126 – hist

Figure S 10: Same as Figures 3a and S8 but for *cex_d (spi6)*.

(a) cex_d (spei6) ssp585 – hist

(b) cex_d (spei6) ssp370 – hist

(c) cex_d (spei6) ssp245 – hist

(d) cex_d (spei6) ssp126 – hist

Figure S 11: Same as Figures 3c and S9 but for *cex_d (spei6)*.

(a) cex_d (spi12) ssp585 – hist

(b) cex_d (spi12) ssp370 – hist

(c) cex_d (spi12) ssp245 – hist

(d) cex_d (spi12) ssp126 – hist

Figure S 12: Same as Figures 3a and S8 but for *cex_d (spi12)*.

(a) *cex_d* (spei12) ssp585 – hist

(b) *cex_d* (spei12) ssp370 – hist

(c) *cex_d* (spei12) ssp245 – hist

(d) *cex_d* (spei12) ssp126 – hist

Figure S 13: Same as Figures 3c and S9 but for *cex_d* (spei12).

8. Appendix II: Regional Projections

Figure A-II-1: Regional projections in the IPCC reference regions (as defined in Iturbide et al. 2020; see also Figure 6) for the Heatwave Amplitude index hwa_tx90 .

Figure A-II-1 (continued)

Figure A-II-1 (continued)

Figure A-II-2: As Figure A-II-1 but for the Heatwave Duration index hwd_tx90.

Figure A-II-2 (continued)

Figure A-II-2 (continued)

Figure A-II-3: As Figure A-II-1 but for the Heatwave Frequency index hwf_tx90.

Figure A-II-3 (continued)

Figure A-II-3 (continued)

Figure A-II-4: As Figure A-II-1 but for the hottest day of the year TXx.

Figure A-II-4 (continued)

Figure A-II-4 (continued)

Figure A-II-5: As Figure A-II-1 but for the annual frequency of warm days TX90p.

Figure A-II-5 (continued)

Figure A-II-5 (continued)

Figure A-II-6: As Figure A-II-1 but for the annual count of months in drought, based on SPI3 (spi3dry).

Figure A-II-6 (continued)

Figure A-II-6 (continued)

Figure A-II-7: As Figure A-II-1 but for the annual count of months in drought, based on SPI6 (spi6dry).

Figure A-II-7 (continued)

Figure A-II-7 (continued)

Figure A-II-8: As Figure A-II-1 but for the annual count of months in drought, based on SPI12 (spi12dry).

Figure A-II-8 (continued)

Figure A-II-8 (continued)

Figure A-II-9: As Figure A-II-1 but for the annual count of months in drought, based on SPEI3 (spei3dry).

Figure A-II-9 (continued)

Figure A-II-9 (continued)

Figure A-II-10: As Figure A-II-1 but for the annual count of months in drought, based on SPEI6 (spei6dry).

Figure A-II-10 (continued)

Figure A-II-10 (continued)

Figure A-II-11: As Figure A-II-1 but for the annual count of months in drought, based on SPEI12 (spei12dry).

Figure A-II-11 (continued)

Figure A-II-11 (continued)

Figure A-II-12: As Figure A-II-1 but for the compound hot and dry events frequency based on SPI3.

Figure A-II-12 (continued)

Figure A-II-12 (continued)

Figure A-II-13: As Figure A-II-1 but for the compound hot and dry events frequency based on SPI6.

Figure A-II-13 (continued)

Figure A-II-13 (continued)

Figure A-II-14: As Figure A-II-1 but for the compound hot and dry events frequency based on SPI12.

Figure A-II-14 (continued)

Figure A-II-14 (continued)

Figure A-II-15: As Figure A-II-1 but for the compound hot and dry events frequency based on SPEI3.

Figure A-II-15 (continued)

Figure A-II-15 (continued)

Figure A-II-16: As Figure A-II-1 but for the compound hot and dry events frequency based on SPEI6.

Figure A-II-16 (continued)

Figure A-II-16 (continued)

Figure A-II-17: As Figure A-II-1 but for the compound hot and dry events frequency based on SPEI12.

Figure A-II-17 (continued)

Figure A-II-17 (continued)